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FROM NATURAL BEEKEEPING TO THE SAN MICHELE ALL'ADIGE
DECLARATION AND DOMUS MELLIFERA PROJECT:
FROM BEEKEEPING TO BIODIVERSITY

*Dall'apicoltura naturale alla Dichiarazione di San Michele all'Adige
e al Progetto Domus mellifera: dall'apicoltura alla biodiversità*

World Biodiversity Association is a non-profit organization founded in 2004 at the Natural History Museum of Verona by a group of botanists, zoologists and Nature lovers. WBA has two missions, *Discovering biodiversity* and *Conservation by Education*, and an International Scientific Committee. In the course of 2010, declared by UN the *International Year of Biodiversity*, WBA proposed “*Biodiversity Friend*” the first certification of biodiversity conservation in agriculture. The standard is based on assessment of the following 10 actions: 1) sustainable agricultural model, 2) conservation of soil fertility, 3) rational management of the water sources, 4) conservation of hedges, woods and nectariferous species, 5) conservation of agrarian biodiversity, 6) energy savings and renewable sources, 7) landscape conservation, 8) social sustainability, 9) economic sustainability, 10) quality of soil, water and air.

The impact of the production process on soil, water and air is evaluated applying the WBA Biodiversity Indexes: the Soil Biodiversity Index (SBI-bf), the Freshwater Biodiversity Index (FBI-bf), the Lichen Biodiversity Index (LBI-bf).

In 2015 January 18, at Pergine Valsugana (Trento - Italy), WBA and E. Mach Foundation presented the “*Bees for Biodiversity Project*” to spread natural and backyard beekeeping and create awareness on the ecological role of *Apis mellifera*. Three years later, 2018 June 12, WBA contributed to the writing of the “*Carta di San Michele all'Adige*”, a scientific document to protect the

diversity of the autochthonous subspecies of *Apis mellifera* in Italy. In 2019, a Technical Committee for the protection of autochthonous bees named CTSTAA (Comitato Tecnico Scientifico Tutela Api Autoctone) was formed within WBA. Main objective of the Committee is to spread the fundamental role of the autochthonous subspecies of *Apis mellifera* in agrosystems and ecosystems, conserving their genetic variability. The safeguard of the bees and pollinators is a topic of scientific, social and ethycal relevance and must be supported by solid scientific foundations.

Finally, in 2020, May 20, WBA presented a new management tool for beekeepers, the *Biodiversity Friend Beekeeping* Certification, based on assessment of 10 principles related to: 1) Limitation of colony migration, 2) Local bees, 3) Material of hives and origin of wax, 4) Formation and multiplication of colonies, 5) Massal/natural selection, 6) Preference for natural or artificial swarms, 7) Reduction of artificial nutrition and biological control of *Varroa*, 8) Territory honey, multifloral honey and reduction of honey processing, 9) Registration of beekeeping operations, 10) Teaching activities on environmental topics related to bees. This bee-friendly and natural hive management respect the bee as a raised but not-domesticated animal pollinator and acknowledges bees their fundamental role in the agrosystems.

Honey bees should be considered and treated also as a wild animal, therefore wild colonies should be protected by farmers and law. In 2021 WBA lauched the *Domus mellifera* Project, dedicated to people (primarily beekeepers and farmers), associations, communities, organic districts, research institutions, charities and public bodies with the function of protecting and governing the territory and biodiversity (National, Municipal and Regional parks, public oases, municipalities, regions, etc.).

The *Domus mellifera* is an artificial wood nest for wild honey bees that can be positioned in agrosystems or natural areas for giving a refuge to wild swarms of bees. The installation and monitoring of the *Domus mellifera*, are actions that can be summarized as being “*guardian of the honey bees*”, a synergistic expression of all: people, nature and actions.

In 2021 the first installation of 11 *Domus mellifera* was launched on Elba Island, in collaboration with the Tuscan Archipelago Section of World Biodiversity Association and Parco Nazionale Arcipelago Toscano (PNAT). Contemporarily WBA promoted and shared the Project in a scientifically correct way, by means of free training courses on natural beekeeping. Since 2021 everyone can also contribute to monitoring wild honey bee colonies using the *BeeWild* app, implemented by E. Mach Foundation and WBA. Hundreds of Italian reports were collected in the *BeeWild* app during the first years of the Project.

Building a detailed map of the distribution of the unmanaged colonies

of *Apis mellifera* will also help to evaluate the effects of the sudden climate changes that have been witnessed in these decades. *BeeWild* aims not only to census and monitor but also to protect the unmanaged populations of honey bees, populations that will be crucial to preserve the local genetic heritages of *Apis mellifera*, the only ones that, under the effect of natural selection, can guarantee adaptation to local conditions and at the same time to changing climatic conditions.

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